

The effectiveness of contact tracing to reduce transmission of infectious disease as part of epidemic or pandemic response: a rapid systematic review: plain language summary.

Background

Infectious diseases can spread through various routes, e.g. air particles, through food or water, from direct touch from one person to another or through bodily fluids such as blood. Several actions can help stop the spread of infectious diseases. One of these is contact tracing (CT), which can be used by governments, communities, and individuals. When someone is infected, the people close to them are the most likely to catch the disease. They may then pass it on to others. CT identifies these people and follows up with them, suggesting they get tested and treatment, if needed. However, it is unclear how good CT is at reducing the spread of infectious diseases, and if there may be any unexpected effects. We looked at the evidence on CT for any infectious disease that could cause an epidemic (a disease that spreads quickly and affects many people within an area) or pandemic (an epidemic that spreads affecting multiple countries and continents, becoming a global issue). Better understanding about which CT methods work is important to help governments and health authorities prepare more effectively for future epidemics or pandemics.

Our approach

We searched for studies involving CT for infectious diseases that could cause epidemics or pandemics. We focused on studies of CT carried out in community settings. We only included studies which compared two groups: one type of CT to another, or to no CT. To see how well CT works, we included studies that measured:

1. how the disease spread (for example, new cases),
2. use of healthcare services (such as emergency admissions), or
3. any unexpected effects (such as unemployment, or partner violence).

We included the best available evidence from studies where both groups were tested during the same period. We collected key information from the studies and measured their quality, including how well they were carried out. We also looked at whether the studies reported health inequalities linked to age, gender, ethnicity, or race, and whether CT made these inequalities better or worse. We grouped the studies by how the infection spreads and by the type of disease.

Because the studies differed in their design, the people included, and the way they measured how well CT worked, we could not combine and make sense of their results using statistics. We wrote a detailed summary of the results and presented the findings in tables. This review was guided by meetings with a patient and public involvement group.

Our findings

The below diagram shows the total number of relevant studies we found and how many were chosen as being the best available evidence. It shows the breakdown of these studies based on which methods of spread and the types of infections that were covered.

We found no evidence on infections spread by vectors (such as mosquitoes and malaria), direct contact (such as skin-to-skin contact or contaminated surfaces, like norovirus), or through food and water.

We grouped CT methods by whether they were led by a healthcare provider, led by patients, involved home visits, or used technology.

More than half of the studies were rated as low quality.

Overall, most studies found that CT did not clearly affect infection control for better or worse. In studies on sexually transmitted infections (STIs), some evidence suggested that healthcare provider-

led CT, such as phone calls to contacts, led to better infection control than patient-led methods, such as referral slips (written information passed directly by the infected individual to their contacts to inform of the risk of infection, and places to go for testing). In studies on tuberculosis, some evidence showed that CT reduced the number of new cases. Only two studies looked at unexpected effects of CT. Both were about sexual health and focused on intimate partner violence (abuse from a former or current sexual partner) or relationship breakdown. There was no difference in intimate partner violence. However, one study reported more relationship breakdowns linked to CT. About 20% of the studies examined health inequalities, however, the data varied widely. There were differences in which groups were included and how the methods were adjusted to account for inequalities. Researchers also varied in how they judged whether these methods worked for different types of inequality. Because of these inconsistencies, it is difficult to draw clear conclusions.

Conclusions

We found that the evidence on how well CT works was mixed and inconsistent. Most studies focused on TB or compared healthcare provider-led and patient-led contact tracing for STIs and HIV.

Because the studies differed so much in design, methods, and how they measured success, it is hard to say which CT strategies work best. It is also unclear how these approaches affect different groups, especially in relation to health inequalities.

More high-quality research is needed to understand what works best and for whom. Researchers should also look more closely at how CT is put into practice and make fairness a key part of its design from the start.